

Experimental Investigation on Performance of a Double Pass Solar Air Heater using Black Coated Porous Wire Mesh as Packed Bed in Rajshahi Division

¹Md. Abdul Monem *, ²Md. Mukul Uddin, ³Md Maruf Tahmid, ⁴Md Sejan Hossain
Department of Mechanical Engineering, Bangladesh Army University of Engineering & Technology (BAUET),
Qadirabad Cantonment, Natore-6431, Bangladesh.

Corresponding Author: ¹Md. Abdul Monem *

Abstract:- In this experimental study, a Double Pass Solar Air Heater utilizing Black Coated Porous Wire Mesh as a packed bed was subjected to rigorous analysis. The research focused on assessing the system's performance using efficiency as a key metric, while also considering the temperature differential between the inlet airflow at ambient condition and outlet airflows. Throughout the investigation, solar intensity was continuously monitored over the course of a day to gauge the availability of solar energy at the experimental location, demonstrating satisfactory levels. Additionally, the heat-absorbing characteristics of the packed bed were scrutinized under three distinct flow rates (0.0115 kg/s, 0.028 kg/s, and 0.038 kg/s). Results indicated that as the flow rate increased, the temperature difference between the inlet and outlet airflows decreased; however, there was a significant increase in efficiency. Notably, the maximum efficiency exhibited a substantial improvement with increasing flow rate, reaching an impressive gain of 120% to 150%. Moreover, the performance of the solar collector exhibited a characteristic trend of increasing to decreasing throughout whole day, corresponding to the varying solar intensity levels.

Keywords:- Solar Air Heater; Packed Bed; Thermal Efficiency; Double Pass Heater, Porous Mesh

I. INTRODUCTION

The consumption of energy is increasing continuously with the growth of the population day by day and for this, the conventional energy sources decrease gradually which is limited. So, we have to find other energy sources which are renewable in nature. Renewable energy resources are solar, wind, tide, biomass, geothermal, biofuel, etc. Solar energy is available among all of them. This vast quantity of renewable energy is twice the conventional energy sources such as fossil fuel, crude oil, mined uranium, and natural gas which are obtained in one year [1]. This huge amount of energy is quite cheap, clean, environment-friendly, pollutants-free, safe, and available in nature. There are various ways to harness solar energy for heating purposes. Two types of

solar technologies are indirect (passive) and direct (active) solar techniques. Without using any mechanical arrangement, passive solar techniques are performed for the heating and cooling of living spaces. These types of techniques contain simple mechanisms and lower installation costs. Active solar air techniques are the processes in which direct electrical energy is obtained. This electrical energy is used for different purposes such as to drive pumps, fans, lights, etc. In these processes, the materials used have a higher installation cost. Solar air heating technology uses an absorbing medium. The efficiency of the solar air heater depends on the properties of the absorbing medium. This absorbing medium captures the sun's energy. When air is passed through the absorbing medium it becomes heated and density is decreased. The applications of air heaters are used to dry fruits, seeds, and vegetables, for room heating, and for industrial purposes [2]. The advantages of solar air heaters are simple design, easy maintenance, no fuel cost, low construction cost, environmentally friendly, zero greenhouse gas emission, and less corrosion. Though this energy is available and massive in the amount it has some drawbacks. The main drawback of solar air heaters is the poor heat transfer rate from the porous media to the air. Another disadvantage is the lower heat transfer coefficient of air than the solid conductor [3].

B. M. Ramani, Akhilesh Gupta, and Ravi Kumar worked on the performance of double-pass solar air collectors and investigated that the performance of double-pass solar air collectors is 25% higher than that of without porous absorbing materials and 35% higher than that of single-pass collectors [4]. L.B.Y Aldabbagh, F. Egelioglu, and M. Ilkan worked on single and double-pass solar air heaters with wire mesh as packed bed and got maximum thermal efficiency 83.64% (double pass) and 45.93% (single pass) at mass flow rate 0.038 kg/sec [5]. Ebrahim M Ali Alfegi *et al.* worked on a transient mathematical model of both side single-pass and double-pass photovoltaic thermal air collectors [6]. They found efficiency of that combined photovoltaic thermal efficiency is increasing from 26.6% to 39.13% as the mass flow rate varies from 0.0316 to 0.09 kg/s [7]. Wijesundera *et al.* represent experimental and analytical analysis of a double-pass solar air collector with

two glass covers. They show that the collector thermal efficiency is increased from 10 to 15% [8]. Ehsan Mohseni Languri et al. presented that thermal efficiency of a double-pass solar air heater with porous material is 40 % higher than the non-porous air heater [9]. Manish Parmar et al. presented that the combined rib-groove roughed geometry gives 10% more efficiency as compared to the smooth absorber plate used in the DPSAH [10]. Yeh HM et al. presented that for a double pass solar air heater, the thermal efficiency can be achieved very well when the cross-sectional area of the upper and lower channels is constructed equally and the air mass flow rates is same [11]. Sopian K. et al. works on porous-nonporous media and evaluates thermal efficiency of double pass solar air collector. They obtained high thermal efficiency solar air collector [12]. Mohamad who referred the conventional double pass collector as a counter-current solar collector showed that the thermal efficiency can be improved by 18% compared to the conventional solar heater. The study also suggested an extra fan power of 2 ± 3 W, which is not high [13]. Madhukeshwara. N et al. represent the performance of a solar air collector with different surface coating and they recommended that the black paint is the most absorptive and less reflective coating [14]. B. M. Ramani, Akhilesh Gupta, and Ravi Kumar recommended that the double pass arrangement without porous media is more efficient than the single pass arrangement [15]. Also, L.B.Y Aldabbagh, F. Egelioğlu, and M. Ilkan suggested that the double pass solar air heater with wire mesh as a packed bed gives the maximum efficiency compared to nonporous media [16].

The thermal efficiency of the air heater depends on the dimension of the collector plate, the material of the collector plate, solar radiation, tilting position, environmental conditions, insulation, etc. If the collector medium is highly conductive, the tilting position is at a right angle with the solar radiation and the insulation is proper then we can get the highest thermal efficiency of the solar air heater. To the best of the author's knowledge, it has been found that there

is no literature available that is related to the black coated wire mesh as a packed bed in the double pass solar air heater. The aim of this study is to design a double-pass solar air heater and to improve the efficiency of the air heater by using black-coated wire mesh as a packed bed on the absorbing plate.

II. EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

Firstly, a wooden box has been made which base was covered by wood of 1.343m^2 . The box was sufficiently rigid to take the load of cover glass, collector sheet and other arrangements. Then a layer of glass wool has been given upon the wooden box as thick as half inch. A 1.27 cm (0.5 inch) thickness of foam is set upon the glass wool. For good insulating a 1.27cm (0.5 inch) cork sheet is adjusted upon the foam. Finally, a 6mm thickness of plywood is covered upon the cork sheet. After that 1mm black coated Galvanized Iron (GI) sheet used as absorbing plate was hardly adjusted upon the plywood through the wooden box. A packed bed wire mesh with a black coat of 4.5 cm thickness, 6.858 m length and 0.7874 m width was set upon the GI sheet which acts as a porous material. Then 2 pieces of 3.5 mm thickness of transparent glass plates are set as the distance between them was 21mm. Two passages have been connected by U turn made up of aluminum sheet and to avoid the heat losses to the surroundings. Sides of the solar collector are made up of 25 mm thick wood to reduce the heat losses to the surroundings. Two GI pipe of 3.5 cm diameter have been used as inlet and outlet portion. The photographic view of glass wool, foam, GI sheet and cork sheet have been shown by figure 1. A centrifugal blower has been used to draw the ambient air into the collector through the entrance section.

Finally, the collector has been supported on a frame made up of M.S. iron angle. The complete experimental setup can be shown by figure 2.

Fig 1 (a) Photograph of Glass Wool 0.5 Inch; (b) Photograph of Foam 0.5 Inch; (c) Photograph of Black Coated GI Sheet 1 mm; (d) Photograph of Cork Sheet 0.5 Inch.

Fig 2 The Experimental Setup

The working principle of a double-pass solar air heater is that, when sunlight falls upon the upper glass plate, more amount of heat is transferred through glass plate to upper pass and makes the pass heated. At the same time, the trapped solar energy from the upper pass is transferred to the absorber plate at lower pass-through middle glass plate. As a result, lower pass becomes more heated. When air is supplied to inlet port by blower, it expands in the upper pass and absorb heat. Then the partially heated air passes through the lower pass. While passing through the lower pass, maximum amount of heat is absorbed. Finally, the hot air is exhausted through exit port.

The inlet and outlet temperature of air has been measured by a pyrometer which has high sensitivity. The temperature of different points such as 1st layer middle temperature, 2nd layer middle temperature, combination temperature of the two layers have been measured by the thermometer whose temperature range was zero to hundred and ten degrees centigrade.

To measure the mass flow rate, the anemometer propeller was placed at the outlet of the blower. The velocity recorded by the anemometer was used in the following formula $m = \rho Av$ (where, ρ =density of air, A = cross sectional area, v = velocity of air). Here the density of air at the ambient condition and the cross-sectional area of the inlet port were known. By this way we measured the mass flow rate. For a fixed mass flow rate, the velocity was different for the variation of temperature.

The data was recorded for different mass flow rate at a time interval of 30 minutes. For the fixed tilt angle the heater was not at normal position with the sun all time. The intensity of the sun in a day which was irregular in nature due to cloudy sky.

III. THERMAL ANALYSIS

The thermal performance of solar collector is measured by rate of heat extracted by the air flow which is measure by the equation written as

$$Q = \dot{m}C_p\Delta T = \rho AV C_p\Delta T$$

Where, ρ stands for density of air, C_p is specific heat at constant pressure, ΔT is the Temperature difference between air inlet and air outlet, V is the velocity of air and inlet pipe area is given by A . Mass flow rate is determined from the equation of $m = \rho Av$.

Now efficiency is measured as a performance evaluation criterion in this study which is defined by the ratio of heat extracted by airflow to available solar energy imparted on collector surface. Efficiency is given by,

$$\eta_c = \frac{\dot{m}C_p\Delta T}{IA_c}$$

Where A_c is the collector area of wire mesh which is effective area to absorb solar radiation estimated by,

$$A_c = A_w - A_o,$$

Where total opening area, A_o and A_w is wire mesh with opening. And I is the solar intensity(w/m^2).

Porosity is measured as ratio of volume of wooden box to opening space of lower pass, where opening space of lower pass is difference between volume of wooden box (lower pass) and solid wire mesh volume $V_{sw} = A_w * t - A_o * t$, t is the thickness of mesh. A decrease in porosity increases the volumetric heat transfer coefficient. The top view and side view sketch drawing of the double-pass solar air heater is shown in Fig 1.

Fig 3 Sketch Drawing of Double Pass Solar Air Heater (a) Top View; (b) Side View

IV. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The solar air heater with wire mesh as packed bed was investigated experimentally from 15.04.2016 to 25.05.2016 under weather condition of Rajshahi located at 24.7106° N,88.9414° E. The readings were taken at the bright sunshine day. Air velocity was sufficient due to use of blower. The performance of a solar air heater has been investigated under three different mass flow rates. The mass flow rate was varied 0.0115 kg/s, 0.028 kg/s and 0.038 kg/s.

In Fig 4 solar air intensity is illustrated with local time all day long i.e., from 9:00 am to 4:00 pm. Solar intensity is a measure of solar energy coming from sun to the experimental setup. As this is the primary criteria to get enough solar heating performance from solar collector this study firstly focuses on this crucial fact. It is observed that solar intensity holds a sharp rising trend at early hours of the day then it attains its highest peak value of 1137.6 W/m² at noon when it is 12:30 which is almost 23% higher than the solar intensity at 9:00 am. After that it gradually decreases as the sun moves away from overhead position and eventually makes up an average solar intensity of around 1050 W/m². That indicates that experimental condition in sense of solar energy availability was very favorable.

Fig 4 Variation of Solar Intensity (W/m²) with Local Time (hour)

Temperature rise i.e, difference in inlet and outlet temperature of air flow for different mass flow rate is shown in Fig 5. Temperature difference of air flow is actually the indication of heat energy absorbed by the black coated porous collector bed since as much as the collector can absorb heat from solar radiation air will get hotter when it flows over the bed surface. That's why absorbed heat is calculated from this analogy. From Fig 5 it is clearly observable that with time from morning to mid-day, temperature difference gradually increases however it decreases afterwards. This trend is expected as temperature difference as well as absorbed energy solely depends on the solar light intensity which shows the likewise trend with time as we discussed earlier. Temperature difference rise is over 10°C from morning to mid-day for all flow rates. Additionally, with increasing flow rate temperature difference drops in significant scale. Because as the air moves away faster from the collector bed it can extract less amount of heat due to lower available time.

Fig 5 Variation of Temperature Difference with Local Time (hour) for Different Flow Rates.

Collector performance is evaluated by the term efficiency which is actually the ratio of heat energy carried away by the airflow to the solar energy that reaches to the collector. Efficiency is demonstrated in Fig 6 with local time for three flow rates. It is found that with time efficiency gradually improves up to a certain value called maximum efficiency point then drops again. At early morning efficiency is not more than 70% for every flow rate considered and at afternoon time it is almost similar to early morning. With variation of flow rate For higher flow rate efficiency is obtained greater for higher values of flow rate however improvement of efficiency is more remarkable when variation occurs in lower range of flow rate. It can be observed that almost 100% increase in efficiency at all local time when flow rate is increased from 0.0115 to 0.028 kg/s and from 0.028 to 0.038 kg/s, only 16% higher efficiency can be obtained.

V. CONCLUSION

In this thermal study, solar heat absorbing performance of double pass air heater with black coated porous wire mesh is evaluated through parameters like efficiency and temperature difference for different flow rate throughout the whole day. The available solar energy is primarily estimated in terms of solar intensity to track the incoming energy. The following points can be noted as concluding remarks of this study. With an average sun intensity of around 1050 W/m², solar energy was sufficient for this study. Temperature difference shows an increasing to decreasing trend with local time attaining its peak at mid-day and with variation of flow rate, temperature difference drops remarkably. Efficiency variation with local time follows the similar trend like temperature difference. Additionally, the maximum efficiency improves significantly with the increase of mass flow rate.

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Fig 6 Variation of temperature difference with Local Time (hour) for different flow rates.

In Fig 7 maximum efficiency for different flow rate is presented. It is observed that maximum efficiency varies significantly with flow rate. At 0.0115 kg/s flow rate, efficiency is around 32% whereas increasing of only 0.016 kg/s flow rate, efficiency improvement is 120% and for another 0.01 kg/s addition to the flow rate the efficiency improvement reaches to 150%.

Fig 7 Variation of Maximum Efficiency with Mass Flow Rates (kg/s)

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